

PECULIARITIES OF ARCHITECTURE AND HISTORY OF RESTORATION OF KYZYL MAZAR MAUSOLEUM IN TASHKENT REGION

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Abstract: This article presents little-studied archival data on the Kyzyl Mazar mausoleum, reveals the architectural peculiarities and uniqueness of the monument, and investigates the stages and methods of its restoration. It also details brief folk legends related to the construction of this little-studied mausoleum located in Babur (Takachi) village of Bekabad district of Tashkent region.

Keywords: mausoleum, Kyzyl mazar, Babur village, hujra, ganch, stalactites, balkhi dome, mausoleum-khanaka, portal-dome, archeology, restoration.

One of the major architectural monuments, known as Kyzyl Mazar, is erected in a deserted area of an old cemetery near the village of Babur (Takachi) in Bekabad district of Tashkent region. By architectural type – it is a mausoleum-khanaka portal-dome composition, which were built in Maverannahr and in particular in the Tashkent region in the 16 th –17 th centuries¹.

Generalization of little-studied archival documents and data of scientific research of the mausoleum-khanaka gave the following picture of its construction and research. This construction has a short history of study – it was first discovered in 1969 when K.A. Abdullaev was compiling a map of monuments in the Tashkent region. Later, in 1970, L.Y. Mankovskaya and A.R. Muhammedjanov inspected and measured the building². In 1992-1993, the Monument Protection Department of Uzbekistan carried out research and restoration work on the monument. Also in 1970 L.Y. Mankovskaya published an article “Мавзолей Кызыл Мазар и Гумбез-бобо (*Mausoleum of Kyzyl Mazar and Gumbез-bobo*)”³, and in 1983 she described it in the book “Памятники зодчества Ташкента XIV-XIX вв (*Monuments of architecture of Tashkent 14th-19th centuries*)” in a monograph published jointly with V.A. Bulatova. In 1987, L.Y. Mankovskaya investigated the Kyzyl Mazar mausoleum and recorded its passport as a historical monument. During the inspection of the cemetery around the mausoleum were found fragments of unglazed and glazed ceramics dating from the 15th-18th centuries⁴.

There are folk legends associated with this monument. They link the Kyzyl Mazar mausoleum with the name of Sultan Zahridin Muhammad Babur of the Timurid dynasty, the

¹ Yusupova M. Medieval architecture. Kyzyl mazar mausoleum. // Tashkent region: the history of civilization and the perspectives of progress. Taskent, 2014. Pp. 90-115. (p. 112-113).

² Буряков Ю.Ф., Касымов М.Р., Ростовцев О.М. Археологические памятники Ташкентской области. Издательство «Фан» Узбекской ССР Ташкент, 1973. С. 102.

³ Маньковская Л.Ю. Мавзолей Кызыл Мазар и Гумбез-бобо. //ОНУ, №10, Ташкент, 1970. С. 70-72.

⁴ Маньковская Л.Ю. Паспорт. Мавзолей Кызыл мазар. Архив ИИск. АН РУз. АН РУз. ИА(М)М24 №770/24. Ташкент, 1987. Стр. 1-5.

founder of the Mughal Empire. According to one of the legends, during Babur's campaign to India, one of his prominent commanders died when leaving Andijan, to whom the mausoleum was dedicated. According to another legend, on the place where Babur's kishlak (former Takachi) now stands, Babur's troops, going to India, fought with Andijans. The battle lasted several days. One of the warriors stood out for his courage, who turned out to be a beautiful Indian girl. She conquered Babur's heart, but died. In honor of her, by order of Babur, they built a mausoleum, which was called Kyzyl Mazar.

However, no evidence of the reliability of the information contained in these hypotheses and legends has been found.

Architect Liya Yulievna Mankovskaya characterizes the architecture of this khanaka, located near the crossing of the Syrdarya River and probably later became a place of pilgrimage. L.Y. Mankovskaya included the monument in the group of mausoleum-khanaka of the 16th-17th centuries with a square plan and a modest portal.

Khanaka-mausoleums with a large domed hall were convenient for Sufi⁵ rejoicings, arched entrance openings with deep passages from four and side rooms, reminiscent of the arrangement of the Khanaka-mausoleum of Zayniddin-Bobo in Tashkent. One can agree with this opinion, since these places of crossing the Syr Darya were located on the caravan route and had the character of pilgrimage settlements. There are also hypotheses that the six burials in the khanaka could have been placed later⁶.

The mausoleum-khanaka Kyzyl Mazar contains a composition unique for Tashkent architecture - a monument with a structure marked by a central dome and a modest portal slightly projecting forward. Also the type of central composition has long been known in Central Asian architecture, the first known mausoleum is shown in the mausoleum of Ismail Samanid in Bukhara^{7,8}. The compositional idea of a square centric mausoleum with a weakly developed portal entrance was inherent in the era of Timur: such is one of the famous mausoleums on the territory of Samarkand of this time - Ruhabad (80th years of the 14th century)⁹. Its flat, as if symbolic portal, decorated in a niche with a stalactite vault, emphasizes one of the four arched entrances to the monument (two of them were laid during repairs) and faces south. This type of composition is used in the large mausoleum-khanaka Kyzyl Mazar. As L.Y. Mankovskaya pointed out, the theme of a closed square in plan mausoleum with a weakly expressed low portal entrance was peculiar to the Tashkent oasis in later periods, in the 18th and 19th centuries. On the one hand, it was manifested later in the Tashkent mausoleums of Khairabad-ishan and Khoja Alambardor¹⁰.

In general, the architectural structure of the mausoleum-khanaka Kyzyl Mazar is a combination of a centric cube-shaped volume, opened on all four sides by doorways in the centers of the niches of the cross-shaped hall, with a small volume of modestly protruding

⁵ Аббасова-Юсупова, М. А. Малоизвестные суфийские комплексы бухарского оазиса XVIII–XIX веков: формирование, архитектура, типология.

⁶ Мавзолей «Кызыл Мазар». «УзНИПИИ реставрация». Книга II, Том I. Архив АКН РУз. Т7321/Я-16, Тошкент, 1993. С. 3-63.

⁷ Аббасова-Юсупова М.А. Бухарская школа зодчества XV-XVII вв. (особенности и динамика развития). Самарканд, 2022.

⁸ Abbasova-Yusupova, M. A. (2023). *Ҳазіра Memorial Complexes in Mawarannahr: Evolution and Architectural Features*. In *Memory and Commemoration across Central Asia* (pp. 222-241). Brill.

⁹ Пугаченкова Г.А., Ремпель Л.И. Выдающиеся памятники архитектуры Узбекистана. Ташкент, 1958. с.106.

¹⁰ Булатова В.А., Маньковская Л.Ю. Памятники зодчества Ташкента XIV-XIX вв. Издательство литературы и искусства, Ташкент, 1983. С.129-131.

portal (its upper part was not preserved and was restored). The width of the niches in the only room of the mausoleum is developed almost to the size of the side of the subdome square, with 25 cm wide corners left from the walls. In the corners of the main volume there are four spiral staircases with variously arranged entrances (three from the rear, southern facade, and one from the interior, from the western side). In one of these staircases, the roof access is open from the exterior west façade of the building, while the other three are enclosed and re-roofed in the “balkhi” style. There are 6 burials located inside the building.

The facades of the monument were not designed for cladding, they are made in the texture of brickwork. Ornamental detailing in the form of flat arched niches on the sides of the doors and four-bay arcading on top of the walls is repeated on the three secondary facades. The facade of the portal pylons on the main façade has been flared with flat recessed niches alternating with square panels.

The mausoleum is built of burnt tile bricks (25x2, 5x5-5.5 cm) on loess mortar. The arches and the dome are built on ganche mortar. The dome overlapping the hall is single, sphero-conical, the transition to it from the square of the hall is realized by false-spherical sails laid out by ring masonry.

The total area of the building: 11.3x11.3m. The total height of the monument is about 11 meters, the height of the walls is 7.2 meters, the width of the portal is 8.5 meters, the span of its vault is 5.4 meters.

The interior of the room is made without plaster and decorations. Inside the room there are several tombstones, the axis of which slightly deviates from the direction of the symmetry axis of the mausoleum.

In 1992, the research and design institute of restoration of cultural monuments of Uzbekistan “UzRDI restoration” carried out technical survey works for the purpose of scientific survey and design and survey works, as well as landscaping works in full for the restoration project of the Kyzyl Mazar site.

In this case, members of the commission (architects M.Shokirov, F.Mukhamedjanov, S.Akhmedova) according to the results of the inspection of the building found that: the external architectural and structural condition of the monument is unsatisfactory, from the outside, the scarp around the monument poured concrete thickness of 30-40 cm, 60 cm above ground level. At the four corners of the building 4 pillars (iron) are made of concrete mixture, which are connected to each other at the roof level; the clay mixture in the joints of brickwork was washed away by rains and weathered, so the joints deepened; some parts of the dome were damaged. The internal architectural and structural condition of the monument was also unsatisfactory: the lower and upper parts of the walls were eroded and damaged; the plaster of the dome vault surface fell off; the stair steps were damaged, the entrance parts of the three external staircases were bricked up, doors and windows were missing, the interior decoration was not preserved. Inside the hall there are 6 brick sagana (burial vaults) with arched end, plastered with clay-saman mortar. Based on the deplorable condition of the monument, it was decided in 1992 to immediately carry out scientific restoration work on it¹¹.

Until 1992, local residents made irregular repairs to the memorial building.

¹¹ Мавзолей Кызыл Мазар. Первоначальные работы и передаточные документы. «УзНИПИ реставрация». Книга I, Том I. Архив АКН РУз. Т7326/Я-90, Тошкент, 1992. С. 6-41.

In 1993, the following works were carried out on the khanaka-mausoleum of Kyzyl Mazar according to the preliminary project: the missing part of the portal was calculated by geometric analysis and then restored; the vaults in the room under the dome were restored, the floors were covered with burnt brick, the joints between the bricks in the walls of the room were filled with ganch, one staircase located inside the walls of the room was repaired, as well as the rest of the staircases with entrances from outside; the exit to the roof was left from one of the staircases, the others were closed. On the facades: late repair layering on the walls was removed and damaged fragments were restored in the style of the preserved brickwork; repair tabs of door and window openings in the walls were removed, windows and doors were repaired; restoration of the dome was limited to replacement of brick rivets on top of it and waterproofing measures, as the structural condition of the dome was good. It should be noted that the doors and bars in the window openings were made according to traditional ancient methods and put in place. Improvement works were carried out around the architectural monument¹².

In conclusion we can draw the following conclusions:

- Kyzyl Mazar monument by architectural typology is a mausoleum-khanaka of portal-dome composition, characteristic of Islamic architecture of Central Asia in the late medieval period;
- L.Y. Mankovskaya dates this monument to the 16th-17th centuries and attributes it to the local type of khanaka-mausoleums of the Tashkent oasis;
- Over time, the building has suffered significant losses, losing the upper part of the portal, ancient doors and arched lattices;
- It is not known exactly to whom the mausoleum is dedicated, although folk legends attribute it to the time of Babur (i.e. the first half of the 16th century)¹³ and associate it with a warlord or a warrior girl.

The geographical location of the monument – on the caravan road at the crossing of the Syrdarya River in the very crowded village of Takachi (now Babur) was once the main stopping place on the caravan route. In general, the architecture of the monument can be attributed to the beginning of the 16th century, but for clarification it is necessary to conduct additional laboratory and archaeological research.

According to F.M. Mukhamedjonova, the chief specialist of engineering surveys in 1993 for this monument, concrete was roughly laid under the walls of the building from the outside. At present the concrete is covered with marble cladding – concrete and marble attract water and do not allow the building to “breathe”. Instead of all this, a 1.5-2 meter wide brick pavement should have been arranged along the exterior wall¹⁴, and to eliminate the moistening of the facade walls, the joints of the ancient brickwork should have been sealed with a ganche mixture¹⁵.

Taking into account the fact that the weather at the location of the mausoleum is rainy and strongly windy, it is necessary to carry out regular supervision and competent ongoing repair

¹² Мавзолей «Кызыл Мазар». «УзНИПИ реставрация». Книга II, Том I. Архив АКН РУз. Т7321/Я-16, Тошкент, 1993. С. 3-63.

¹³ Булатова В.А., Маньковская Л.Ю. Памятники зодчества Ташкента XIV-XIX вв. Издательство литературы и искусства, Ташкент, 1983. С.129-131.

¹⁴ Мавзолей «Кызыл Мазар». «УзНИПИ реставрация». Книга II, Том I. Архив АКН РУз. Т7321/Я-16, Тошкент, 1993 й. С. 3-63.

¹⁵ Каландарова, Н. Г. (2023). Применение традиция «наставник–ученик» в реставрации архитектурных памятников (на примере Бухарской школы). *Central asian journal of arts and design*, 211-218.

work. We hope that the little-studied materials on the architecture and restoration of the monument, as well as recommendations presented in the article can serve in the future in the development of competent science-based design solutions with the restoration and restoration of its original architectural appearance.

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